

New Substitution Products of $K_3[Cr(SCN)_6]$ with some Higher Aliphatic Monoamines

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The gradual substitution of the ionic bonded thiocyanato groups in the $[Cr(SCN)_6]^{3-}$ complex with mono- and polydentate anionic and neutral ligands leads to the formation of complex cations, anions and non-electrolytes following the Werner-Mirolati's transition series $[Cr(SCN)_6]^{3-}$, $[Cr(SCN)_{6-n}X_n]^{3-}$ ($X = CN, NCSe, Cl$), $[Cr(SCN)_5A]^{2-}$, $[Cr(SCN)_4A_2]^-$, $[Cr(SCN)_3A_3]^0$, etc. ($A = \text{amine, phosphine, } H_2O, NH_3$)¹. The reinecke salt $NH_4[Cr(SCN)_4(NH_3)_2] \cdot H_2O^2$ and their analogous compounds present analytical importance.

Earlier we described³ a series of new substitution products of the anhydrous $K_3[Cr(SCN)_6]$ with heterocyclic amines and phosphines obtained in molten state and in solutions respectively. The mentioned ligands (L) react without solvent following the equation,

Results and Discussion

Our preparative study to obtain analogous derivatives of reinecke salt in aqueous, alcoholic solutions using aliphatic amines gave only negative results. The reaction with higher aliphatic amines n-hexylamine, n-heptylamine and n-octylamine respectively with basicity constants⁴ 4.4×10^{-4} , 4.6×10^{-4} and 4.5×10^{-4} , led to the precipitation of $Cr(OH)_3$ from $K_3[Cr(SCN)_6]$. These anhydrous amines reacted easily without solvent with $K_3[Cr(SCN)_6]$. The complex anions $[Cr(SCN)_4(\text{n-hexylamine})_2]^-$, $[Cr(SCN)_4(\text{n-heptylamine})_2]^-$ and $[Cr(SCN)_4(\text{n-octylamine})_2]^-$ were characterised by double-exchange reactions.

A series of new salts with the hydrochlorides of

heterocyclic N-bases and cobalt(III)amine bases of the hexamine, monoacidopentamine and diacidotetramine types were obtained (Tables 1 and 2).

The amine• $H[Cr(SCN)_4(\text{amine})_2]$ type salts with N-bases are red-violet crystalline substances. The solubility of these reinecke salt like compounds is influenced by the nature of the amine bonded in the outer coordination sphere. The solubility in water of the salts with identical N-bases decreases in the following order: amine• $H[Cr(SCN)_4(\text{n-hexylamine})] >$ amine• $H[Cr(SCN)_4(\text{n-heptylamine})_2] >$ amine• $H[Cr(SCN)_4(\text{n-octylamine})_2]$. This phenomenon is in agreement with the increasing hydrophobic character of the $[Cr(SCN)_4(\text{amine})_2]^-$ anion with the increase of $-CH_2-$ chainlength of the aliphatic amine. These derivatives are much more soluble in water as compared to the analogous salts having aromatic and heterocyclic amines as ligands. Comparison of the electronic spectra of the $K_3[Cr(SCN)_6]$ with those of the reinecke ones, shows a shift of the absorption band in the visible region from blue-violet to red. The nature of the coordinated amine influences only a little.

The electronic spectra of reineckesalts were taken in ethanol (the concentration range from 2×10^{-2} to $1 \times 10^{-4} M$) at about 30 min after dissolution at room temperature using a Specord spectrophotometer. The bands were found at 534, 410 and 310 nm. The first band shifted towards shorter wavenumbers in comparison to that of $K_3[Cr(SCN)_6]$ ($\lambda_1 = 545-550 \text{ nm}$). The 410 and 310 nm bands appeared in the spectra of both the complexes. The results are presented in Table 3.

In the infrared spectra of the $NH_4[Cr(SCN)_4-$

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE AMMONIUM SALTS OF THE TYPE AMINE•H[Cr(SCN)₄(AMINE)₂]

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
	S	N	Cr
Pyridine.HA	22.52	17.20	9.10
(Red-violet)	(22.63)	(17.29)	(9.17)
γ -Picoline.HA	21.97	16.80	8.91
(Red-violet)	(22.08)	(16.87)	(8.95)
2,6-Lutidine.HA	21.48	16.36	8.72
(Red-violet)	(21.55)	(16.47)	(8.74)
Piperazine.HA	22.21	19.48	9.00
(Red-violet)	(22.34)	(19.51)	(9.06)
Papaverine.HA	15.40	11.80	6.20
(Red-violet)	(15.50)	(11.84)	(6.29)
Pyramidone.HA	17.80	17.44	7.19
(Red-violet)	(17.83)	(17.52)	(7.23)
Vibramycine.HA	13.67	12.00	5.50
(Red-brown)	(13.75)	(12.13)	(5.58)
Tetracycline.HA	13.66	11.94	5.51
(Red-brown)	(13.75)	(12.01)	(5.57)

*A = [Cr(SCN)₄(n-hexylamine)₂]

(amine)₂] the vibration bands of the SCN group and those of the coordinated amines were identified and interpreted. The ν_{CII} and ν_{CS} bands of [Cr(NH₃)₅(SCN)]X₂ and [Cr(en)₂(SCN)₂]X were observed at 2 060–2 080 and 730–760 cm⁻¹ respectively⁵.

The spectra of the reineckeates revealed the ν_{CN} band at 2 080–2 090 cm⁻¹ and the ν_{CS} at 720–760 cm⁻¹. The SCN deformation band appeared at 450–470 cm⁻¹. This phenomenon confirms the chromium-thiocyanate bonding through the nitrogen atom, leading to the linear Cr–NCS grouping. The M–SCN bent bond species appears in the case of the thiocyanato-derivatives of platinum, palladium and mercury⁶. The ν_{NH} vibration of the coordinated aliphatic amines observed at 3 210 and 3 120 cm⁻¹, shifted by 150–200 cm⁻¹ as compared to those of the free, non-coordinated amines (3 500, 3 300 cm⁻¹) (strong covalent Cr–N(amine) bondings). Other bands were observed at 2 860–2 940 (ν_{CH}) and 1 470–1 480 cm⁻¹ (δ_{CH_2}).

Experimental

Preparation of NH₄[Cr(SCN)₄(amine)₂] (amine =

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COBAL(III)-AMINE SALTS OF THE H[Cr(SCN)₄(AMINE)₂] ACIDS

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)		
	S	N	Co+nCr
[Co(NH ₃) ₆].A ₃	23.60	20.59	13.21 ^a
(Yellow-pink)	(23.72)	(20.72)	(13.26)
[Co(en) ₂ Clpy].A ₂	20.09	8.66	12.72 ^b
(Red)	(20.20)	(18.78)	(12.82)
[Co(en) ₂ Cl(imidazole)].A ₂	20.38	19.89	12.91 ^b
(Red-brown)	(20.41)	(20.06)	(12.93)
[Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂].A	17.33	18.88	15.00 ^c
(Light green)	(17.40)	(19.00)	(15.06)
[Co(DH) ₂ (aniline) ₂].A	13.21	17.33	11.48 ^c
(Red-brown)	(13.30)	(17.42)	(11.51)
[Co(DH) ₂ (<i>o</i> -anisidine) ₂].A	12.40	16.41	10.81 ^c
(Brown)	(12.52)	(16.40)	(10.83)
[Co(propox.H) ₂ (aniline) ₂].A	12.83	17.00	11.20 ^c
(Yellow-brown)	(12.99)	(17.03)	(11.24)
[Co(heptox.H) ₂ (pyridine) ₂].A	13.00	17.02	11.22 ^c
(Yellow-brown)	(13.08)	(17.14)	(11.32)

*DH = deprotonated dimethylglyoxime, C₄H₇N₂O₂; Propox.H = deprotonated methylisopropylglyoxime, C₆H₁₁N₂O₂; Heptox.H = deprotonated cycloheptanedione dioxime : C₇H₁₁N₂O₂.

^aCo + 3Cr. ^bCo + 2Cr. ^cCo + Cr.

n-hexylamine, *n*-heptylamine, *n*-octylamine) : A mixture of anhydrous K₃[Cr(SCN)₆] (0.1 mol) and the aliphatic amine (0.3 mol) was stirred frequently. The initial violet colour turned to dark red. In order to separate the product from the KSCN, the mixture was treated with 50% acetic acid (250 ml) after cooling, stirred vigorously and filtered. The precipitate was washed with an aqueous solution of acetic acid and the residue (amine)₂H₂[Cr(SCN)₄(amine)₂]₂ was dissolved in ethanol (200 ml), crystallised and dried in air.

Preparation of derivative of the type amine H[Cr(SCN)₄(amine)₂] : The corresponding amine (10 mmol) was mixed with concentrated HCl (10 ml) and the resulting amine-chlorohydrate was dissolved in water (80–100 ml). NH₄[Cr(SCN)₄(amine)₂] (2.5 mmol) was dissolved in alcohol (30–35 ml) separately. After mixing the above two solutions the complex salt precipitated out within 10–30 min. The resulting solid

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE $\text{NH}_4[\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_4(\text{AMINE})_2]$

Amine	λ_1	$\log \epsilon_1$	λ_2	$\log \epsilon_2$	λ_3	$\log \epsilon_3$	λ_4	$\log \epsilon_4$
	kK		kK		kK		kK	
n-Hexylamine	18.2	2.60	24.4	2.65	31.8	4.50	41.8	4.60
n-Heptylamine	18.0	2.60	24.6	2.70	31.85	4.60	41.0	4.50
n-Octylamine	18.4	2.65	24.6	2.75	31.75	4.65	40.5 ^a	4.40

^aInflexion point.

was washed with some distilled water 3–4 times and dried in air at room temperature (Table 1).

The chromium content was determined iodometrically, sulphur gravimetrically as BaSO_4 and nitrogen by Duma's method.

Synthesis of cobalt(III) amine derivatives :

Hexamincobalt(III) derivatives : To the chloride of the hexamine type complex (2 mmol) dissolved in water (150 ml), was added $\text{NH}_4[\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_4(\text{amine})_2]$ (2 mmol) in alcohol (30 ml). The mixture was allowed to stand for 20–30 min and the product of the double exchange reaction was filtered, washed with water and dried in air.

Monoacidopentamincobalt(III) derivatives : *trans*- $\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2\text{Cl}$ (3 mmol) was treated with the amine (ammonia, pyridine, aniline, benzylamine, imidazol etc.) (3.0–3.5 mmol) at room temperature in 10 ml aqueous solution. After allowing to stand for one day the reaction mixture was diluted to 100 ml and filtered. To the filtrate, a solution of $\text{NH}_4[\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_4(\text{amine})_2]$ (2 mmol) in alcohol (30 ml) was added to yield a precipitate. The above described procedure was followed further.

Diacidotetramincobalt(III) derivatives : To the diacidotetramine complex (in chloride form) (2 mmol) dissolved in water (200 ml) was added $\text{NH}_4[\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_4(\text{amine})_2]$ (2 mmol) in alcohol (30 ml). The resulting complex salts were worked up as described above. The dimethylglyoxime (DH_2) containing cobalt(III) chelate compounds were synthesised by Ablov's method. The aqueous alcoholic solution of cobalt(III) chloride, dimethylglyoxime and the corresponding amine (mo-

lar ratio 1 : 2 : 3) was oxidised by bubbling air through the mixture. The analytical data of the compounds are given in Table 2.

Sulphur and nitrogen were determined as above. The sum of the metals was determined gravimetrically in the form of $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4 + \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ after ignition at 900–920°.

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